

Research Article

NAT2 and Hepatocellular carcinoma: Bioinformatic analysis

Ratan Kumar Rai

University of Kentucky, Lexington, Kentucky, USA

ratana.rai@uky.edu

Abstract- Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) serves as the sixth most common cancer worldwide. N-acetyltransferase 2 (NAT2) plays a significant role in the metabolism of exogenous compounds including therapeutic drugs. The individuals are categorized into fast acetylators and slow acetylator phenotypes based on the acetylation phenotype. The gene expression dataset GSE33294 from GEO was downloaded to understand the Nat2 expression in HCC patient samples. Volcano plot revealed the presence of 700 downregulated and 576 upregulated mRNAs. The Gene Ontology and pathway enrichment analysis showed that upregulated genes were significantly enriched in mitotic cell division, while the down-regulated genes were significantly expressed in drug metabolism, and cell signaling. The result revealed the significantly downregulated expression of Nat2 in HCC patients, implicating poor metabolism of exogenous as well as endogenous compounds in HCC disease. Further molecular analysis related to the drug-metabolizing gene would help in the potential diagnosis and treatment of HCC.

Keywords- N-acetyltransferase, Hepatocellular carcinoma, NCBI, Phenotypes

I. INTRODUCTION

HCC is the most common form of liver disease and accounts for the fourth major cause of cancer-related deaths [1],[2]. Since it is well documented most HCC risk factors (chronic infection with hepatitis B virus (HBV) and/or hepatitis C virus (HCV)) operate by promoting the development of cirrhosis. Not only Virus, but various environmental factors

such as aflatoxin exposure, tobacco use, and decreased antioxidants micronutrients have also been implicated in the etiology of the HCC [3]. Based on several studies, several polymorphic genes are associated with susceptibility to the effects of exposure to certain environmental risk factors on HCC development among chronic HBV carriers [4]. Most of these genes encode drug-metabolizing enzymes and are expressed in the liver. To this respect, arylamine N-acetyltransferases (NAT) are known to be Phase II drug-metabolizing enzymes that catalyze the acetyl transfer from acetyl coenzyme A (acetyl-CoA) to an aromatic amine, heterocyclic amine, and hydrazine compounds [5]. These carcinogens are present in tobacco smoke and formed in the cooking of meats and other sources of animal protein. Humans possess two functional NAT genes, namely, NAT1 and NAT2, located on chromosome 8 (Figure1) [6], [7], [8]. For the drug metabolism process, the individual acetylation phenotype has important bearing; as in the case of fast acetylators, the drugs are effectively used by the body (due to fast acetylation and rapid excretion) leading to a healthy metabolism, while in the case of slow acetylators, the drugs stay unusually long (due to slow acetylation and poor excretion) and thus might lead to drug toxicity and adverse drug reactions. Not only that, but acetylator phenotypes of an individual are also correlated with their respective dietary traditions in a particular population [9], [10]. In comparison to Nat1, Nat2 plays a significant role in the metabolism of a wide variety of xenobiotic compounds including drugs and exogenous chemicals present in the diet and is one of the first enzymes discovered that play a role in inter-individual drug variation [11]. Nat2 is thus considered to be a broad-spectrum drug-metabolizing enzyme (isoniazid, procainamide, hydralazine, sulphonamide, dapsone, para-aminobenzoic acid) and thus present study focussed on NAT2. Several allelic variants of NAT2, which cause variations in acetylation capacity have been associated with different

diseases [12]. Genotypes for slow acetylation were associated with an increased risk of bladder cancer but decreased risk of colorectal cancer [13],[14]. Also, studies showed Nat2 acetylation and the risk of developing HCC in smokers and not in non-smokers [15]. Nat2 acetylation phenotype was also associated with Parkinson's disease [16], Gilbert syndrome [17], Alzheimer's disease [18], peripheral neuropathy, systemic lupus erythematosus [19], diabetes [12], cataract [20], non-Hodgkin lymphoma [21], Schizophrenia [22], etc. Due to such a wide association of the NAT2 gene in drug metabolism and disease association, this gene has been given special emphasis in pharmacogenetics [23]. Evolutionary studies based on NAT2 acetylation phenotype and subsistence mode of strategy and dietary traditions have been well established [24], [25], but the role of Nat2 in HCC is not well understood. It is thus important to understand the role of Nat2 expression patterns in HCC patient samples. This study focused on the Nat2 expression in HCC patient sample of Chinese origin and compared to matched adjacent non-tumorous (NT) tissues. We herewith have utilized the availability of GEO datasets from NCBI and analyzed the expression of genes that are up or downregulated in Hepatocarcinoma (HCC) patients.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

RNA sequencing data of GSE33294 SRA [26] of three HCC patient samples and three adjacent non-tumorous (NT) tissues as control were downloaded from NCBI GEO. The detailed sampling was reported in [26]. After the removal of error alignments from FastQC, high-quality reads were mapped to the human reference sequence (GRCh37/hg19) using software TopHat, and Burrows-Wheeler Aligner (BWA). Differentially expressed genes were analyzed using DESeq2.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

Correlation matrix of six GEO samples (control and HCC) were constructed in the matplotlib module using python programming. The analysis was performed by comparing the values of the entire transcriptome in all six samples [26]. Sample clustering in the form of Heatmap was performed in each control and HCC samples using library gdata and gplots in R Studio. Clustering for samples is shown through the dendrogram tree. The heatmap displays standardized expression values ranging between -2 to +2 with a mean of zero. To observe the up-regulation and down-regulation of

genes, differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were conducted using the DESeq2 library in R. The volcano plot visualization made by fold change ($\log_2\text{foldchange}$, X-axis) and $-\log_{10}P\text{-adj}$, Y-axis). Genes with $\log_2\text{foldchange} \geq 1$, $\text{adjP value} < 0.01$, and $\log_2\text{foldchange} \leq -1$, $\text{adjP value} < 0.01$ by DESeq2 were denoted as differentially expressed genes and represented by Volcano plot. Functional and pathway enrichment analyses were performed using DAVID. Upregulated and Downregulated genes were further used to investigate the Enrichment pathways analysis using DAVID annotation [27]. The Database for Annotation, Visualization, and Integrated Discovery (DAVID, v6.8) is a function enrichment tool that supplies biological explanations of gene lists and proteomic studies from high-throughput sequencing [27]. A P value of <0.05 was the criterion for significance. Also, the mouse disease phenotype was assessed using ToppGene enrichment analysis [28]. Protein-protein interaction network of respective proteins to the top 50 differentially expressed proteins were constructed using the STRING database [29]. Thicknesses of interactions show confidence levels according to the STRING database. Network nodes represent proteins and edges represent protein-protein associations.

IV. RESULTS

To understand the association of NAT2 in Hepatocarcinoma (HCC), we took the advantage of already available RNA genome data from NCBI Geo. The sample correlation matrix measured by Pearson's coefficient (R^2) of the whole dataset ranged from 0.911-1.0 (Figure 2). The gene-gene correlation matrix in the form of heatmap showed 20831 expressed genes (Figure 3). Out of these 20831-mRNA expressed, 1276 mRNAs were found to be significantly differentially expressed in HCC with 700 mRNAs downregulated and 576 were upregulated as shown in the Volcano plot (Figure 4). Surprisingly, we found that Nat2 expression is downregulated in HCC. Also, other drug-metabolizing genes such as Cyp1a2, Cyp3a4 were downregulated.

V. GENE REGULATION SPECIFIC TO PATHWAYS

DAVID functional annotation was used to analyze the functional classification of the 700 downregulated and 576 upregulated DEGs. Gene Ontology showed upregulated DEGs were significantly enriched in cell cycle phase, cell

division, and mitotic nuclear division and downregulated in signaling, glycosylation, drug metabolism, and extracellular matrix (ECM) (Table 1). Signaling including chemokine receptors (e.g CXCR2), complement factors, and ACE2 (angiotensin I converting enzyme). Glycosylation genes such as solute carrier family (e.g. SLC1A2), Sialyltransferase (ST8Sia6, ST3GAL1), and C-type lectin domain family 1(Clec4) are also downregulated. Besides, drug metabolism genes such as CYP (e.g. CYP1A2, CYP3A4) and NAT (NAT2) are also downregulated. Protein-protein interaction network showed a cluster of a drug-metabolizing gene such as Cyp1a2, Cyp3a4, and Nat2 in downregulated genes, whereas upregulated genes showed clustering of genes involved in cell division such as cell division cycle (Cdc) and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) that direct array of stimuli, such as mitogens, cytokines in cellular response (Figure 5). Furthermore, substantial evidence also suggested that the downregulated genes are involved in the abnormal hepatobiliary system in mouse (Table 2).

VI. DISCUSSION

With the rapidly growing high throughput sequencing technologies, genome architecture and their expression patterns of genes are now easily deciphered that helped in combatting and diagnosing diseases [30], [31], [32], [33]. This pattern helped to understand genes and genomes of our species “Homo” but also helped to understand the genome architecture and expression patterns in our evolutionary closest relative great apes [34],[35]. Drug metabolizing genes play a vital role in exogenous compounds' metabolism and diseases [12] and hence it is important to understand the genomic and expression pattern of these genes. Nat2 is a broad-spectrum drug-metabolizing gene and has been considered among genes that are involved in inter-individual drug variation. However, based on its acetylation capacity the individuals are classified as fast and slow metabolizers. Slow metabolizers are often associated with a risk to drug side effects due to slow metabolism and the accumulation of drugs inside the body. On the other hand, fast metabolizers are considered to have no effect of drugs due to fast metabolism. Despite advancements in high throughput technologies, a handful of studies were focused on the association of the Nat2 acetylator phenotype and HCC. While Gilatti et al. (2005) showed no association of NAT2 polymorphisms and HCC risk [36], Yu et al. (2000) showed NAT2*4 (wild type allele) association with HCC in smokers than non-smokers group [15]. This study would provide insights into the expression of Nat2 in HCC patients and its role in the prognosis of the

disease. With the 1276 statistically significant DEGs in HCC samples, 576 genes were upregulated and 700 were downregulated. These down-regulated genes are related to ECM, signaling (GPCRs), metabolic processes, and N-glycosylation. Cell surface glycans play an important role in cell adhesion and development, cell recognition, cancer development, and metastasis [37]. Aberrant glycosylation of the cell surface is associated with the malignant transformation of normal cells, that may serve as a biomarker for, several cancers, as well as offering potential therapeutic targets. Earlier studies reported the number of N- and O-linked glycosylation changes have been associated with carcinogenesis in general and HCC [38], [39]. Since the liver is an active secretory organ and is one of the organs of the secretory glycoproteins, it is likely to be affected by the glycosylation changes. Also, ECM mediated signals were downregulated that are important for tissue gene expression, and the development of cancer. Consistent with the result obtained from downregulated mRNAs, upregulated mRNAs showed involvement in cell cycle, mitotic cell division, that further aid in the liver tissue damage leading to liver cirrhosis.

VII. CONCLUSION

The present study showed the downregulation of drug-metabolizing gene NAT2 in HCC patient samples that indicates aberrant drug metabolism leading to adverse drug reactions and pathogenesis of disease deteriorating tissue and molecular function of the liver.

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Author contribution: The study was conceptualized and analyzed by R.K.R.

Conflict of Interest: Author found no conflict of interest

A. Tables

Table 1: Bioinformatics analysis identifies overrepresented ontology terms in the mRNAs whose abundance differs between HCC and Control.

Down in HCC versus Control		Up in HCC versus Control	
Ontology term	# of genes	Ontology term	# of genes
Cell Signalling	279	Cell cycle	110
Extracellular region	144	Cell division	73
N-Glycosylation	240	Mitotic nuclear division	42
Drug metabolism	28	DNA damage and repair	60

Table 2: Bioinformatics analysis identifies downregulated mRNAs in the Mouse phenotype using ToppGene.

ID	Name	P value	Bonferroni
MP:0005370	liver/biliary system phenotype	1.772E-9	8.690E-6
MP:0002139	abnormal hepatobiliary system physiology	7.572E-9	3.713E-5
MP:0000609	abnormal liver physiology	2.024E-8	9.928E-5
MP:0000598	abnormal liver morphology	3.486E-8	1.710E-4
MP:0002138	abnormal hepatobiliary system morphology	7.062E-8	3.463E-4
MP:0005332	abnormal amino acid level	8.677E-8	4.255E-4
MP:0005311	abnormal circulating amino acid level	3.092E-7	1.516E-3
MP:0002118	abnormal lipid homeostasis	6.229E-7	3.055E-3
MP:0001547	abnormal lipid level	1.437E-6	7.047E-3
MP:0004774	abnormal bile salt level	1.440E-6	7.060E-3

B. Figure

Figure 1: Location of functional NAT genes (NAT1 and NAT2) on chromosome 8. NAT2 gene harbors only one open reading frame that codes for 290 aa NAT2 enzyme.

Figure 2: RNA-Seq Pearson correlation matrix of the whole dataset (six samples). The R2 across all samples ranged between 0.911 to 1.0. Correlation analysis was performed using Matplotlib, Python programming.

Figure 3: Sample clustering in each control and HCC sample was constructed in the form of a heatmap using Heatmap.2 in R. Colours indicate Z-score values with a low expression (green) and high expression (red). Each column represents a sample and each row represents a gene.

Figure 4: Volcano plot showed significant differentially expressed genes (DEGs). A. The X-axis shows the log of statistical significance, and the Y-axis shows the log₂FoldChange in gene expression. Red dots represent upregulated genes and Green dots represent downregulated genes. Blue represents non-significant genes. B. Volcano plot showing the downregulated NAT2 (marked as red and circled).

Figure 5: Protein-protein interaction network of respective proteins to differentially expressed genes (DEG) in cumulus cells from among the groups. Thicknesses of interactions show confidence levels according to the STRING database.

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